

Effects of perceived organisation support, employee engagement and organisation citizenship behaviour on quality performance

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of perceived organisation support, employee engagement, and organisation citizenship behaviour on quality performance of ISO 9001:2000 certified manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. A random sample of 255 shop-floor employees that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study responded. Structural equation modelling was used for the data analysis. It was found that OCB-I mediates the relationship between perceived organisation support and quality performance as well as employee engagement and quality performance. However, the findings suggest that neither perceived organisation support nor employee engagement operate as an antecedent to organisation citizenship behaviour that immediately benefit the organisation in general (OCB-O).

Key words: employee engagement, organisation citizenship behaviour, perceived organisation support, quality performance.

Introduction

Quality management systems have been widely recognized as a fundamental business management strategy to strengthen the competitive position in local as well as global markets (Zelnik et al., 2012). The literature identifies quality certification as the first step towards total

quality management, where the certification can create a good climate to move towards a total quality management system in the long-run (Fotopoulos et al., 2010).

The success of any quality improvement process is heavily influenced by attitudes, perceptions, and behaviours of employees involved in the process (Al-Zoubi, 2012; Green, 2012). Hence, organisations should maintain an environment conducive to employee participation, quality leadership, employee development, and the management of its people to obtain full potential of employees for quality initiatives (Dahlgaard et al., 2011; Zink, 2008; Bou & Beltrán, 2005). However, the literature suggests that many quality efforts do not reach their full potential due to insufficient understanding about the human dimension (Dahlgaard-Park, 2011). Hence, there is a need of understanding psychological and sociological aspects of individuals at work (Dahlgaard-Park, 2012).

The current study investigated the mediating effect of organisation citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the relationship between perceived organisation support (POS) and quality performance and employee engagement and quality performance of ISO 9001:2000 certified manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. The novelty of the study lies in the following aspects. The utilization of business improvement models is associated with a greater reliance on non-financial performance measures such as employees' work-related behaviour, attitudes, and perceptions. However, our review of literature has shown that employee beliefs and attitudes to organisation support, employee engagement, and OCB in the context of quality management have so far gone largely unrecorded. To date, few studies attempted to address these variables (Joiner, 2007). Further, one of the main shortcomings of such previous empirical studies lay that they include a limited number of human dimensions (e.g. POS, OCB) in a single study. Therefore, it is

reasonable to analyze several human dimensions, which have until recently been studied separately, within an extended framework in a single study. As human dimensions in the quality management context present an exciting area of research, we believe that the findings of the study would provide new insights to academics and practitioners worldwide. Further, it is expected that the findings of the study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Perceived organisation support

Perceived organisation support captures an employee's beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values [employees'] general contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 2002, p. 566). In other words, POS focuses on the employer's side of the exchange as perceived by employees. Therefore, an employee's beliefs of how an organisation values him or her is vital for determining whether any attitudes or behaviours benefiting the organisation emerge from the exchange relationship that takes place between the employee and employer (Eisenberger et al., 2002).

It has been argued that POS is affected by the fair allocation of job rewards for the effort employees put in to meet organisational goals, which signify a belief that the organisation values the contribution of its employees (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Job rewards include tangible incentives, such as pay and fringe benefits and socio-emotional benefits such as esteem, supportive and helpful supervision, approval, and caring (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Further, employees value job rewards to be based on the discretion of the organisation rather than being

influenced by external forces, such as unions or health and safety regulations (Dawley et al., 2008). These voluntary job rewards that come directly from the organisation are perceived as an indication that the organisation values employees' contribution made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Dawley et al., 2008).

Employee engagement

In brief, the term employee engagement refers to the individual's involvement and satisfaction with as well as enthusiasm for work. Kahn (1990, p. 694) defined engagement as "the simultaneous employment and expression of a person's 'preferred self' in task behaviours that promote connections to work and to others, personal presence (physical, cognitive, and emotional), and active, full role performances". Hence, employees with engaging behaviours become physically involved in tasks, whether alone or with others, cognitively vigilant, and empathically connected to others (Kahn, 1990, 1992).

Further, according to Kahn (1990, p. 700), an employee's self-expression of preferred dimensions underlies what other researchers referred to as creativity, the use of personal voice, emotional expression, authenticity, non-defensive communication, playfulness, and ethical behaviour. Furthermore, according to Kahn (1990, p. 700) such engagement underlies what other researchers have referred to as effort, involvement, flow, mindfulness, and intrinsic motivation. Overall, engaged employees know what is expected of them, form strong relationships with co-workers and managers, and experience meaning in their work; they are more satisfied and more productive as opposed to disengaged employees.

Organisation citizenship behaviour

Organisation citizenship behaviour is defined as “individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organisation” (Organ, 1988, p. 4). Examples of OCB include, helping co-workers who are behind in their work, offering to help others to accomplish their work, attendance and punctuality beyond requirements, informing others before taking action that would affect their work, gracefully tolerating the minor inconveniences that are an inevitable part of organisational work, voluntarily doing more than the job requires, and appropriate participation in the governance and affairs of the organisation. Therefore, OCB supports the social and psychological environment in which task performance takes place and individuals who spend time on OCB are considered “good citizens” (Organ, 1988). Yet, these extra-role behaviours are not easily enforceable and performing them is usually at the discretion of the individual (Bergeron, 2007; Organ, 1988; Williams & Anderson, 1991).

The literature suggests two salient dimensions of OCB, namely, OCB-O behaviours that benefit the organisation in general (e.g. performing duties that are not required but which improve organisational image and performance) and OCB-I behaviours that immediately benefit specific individuals and indirectly through this means contribute to the organisation (e.g. helping colleagues who have been absent and helping colleagues who have heavier work loads) (Williams & Anderson, 1991, p. 601).

Perceived organisation support and organisation citizenship behaviour. Empirical evidence for the relationship between POS and OCB is mixed. Several past research provide evidence that

employees who perceive a high level of organisation support display increased levels of OCB (Liu, 2009; Suazo and Stone-Romero, 2011; Wayne et al., 1997). For instance, Suazo and Stone-Romero (2011) and Wayne et al. (1997) found a significant positive relationship between POS and OCB, which included both OCB-I and OCB-O. Further, Liu (2009) found a significant positive relationship between POS and OCB-O. However, Settoon et al. (1996) and Lambert (2000) found that POS is unrelated to OCB.

Consistent with the majority of findings of the past research that indicate positive and significant relationship between POS and OCB, it is proposed for the study that employees who feel their organisations value their contributions and care about their welfare tend to reciprocate by engaging in more acts of citizenship behaviour (in terms of both OCB-I and OCB-O) than those having lower levels of POS. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1a: POS is positively related to OCB-I

H1b: POS is positively related to OCB-O

Employee engagement and organisation citizenship behaviour. Few studies investigated the relationship between employee engagement and OCB (e.g. Saks, 2006). For instance, Saks (2006) found significant positive relationship between employee engagement and OCB. However, we have not come across previous studies that investigated the effect of employee engagement on OCB in terms of OCB-I and OCB-O. Based on the literature reviewed earlier, it is proposed for the study that employees who are more engaged tend to reciprocate by involving in more acts of citizenship behaviour. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2a: Employee engagement is positively related to OCB-I

H2b: Employee engagement is positively related to OCB-O

Quality systems

A quality management system incorporates organisational structure, procedures, processes and resources needed to implement quality management. The ISO 9000 series of international quality management standards has earned a reputation as the fundamental requirement in establishing a certified quality management system (Karapetrovic et al., 2010; Kuo et al., 2009) where as total quality management (TQM) constitutes the highest level of quality management system (Lambert & Ouedraogo, 2008, p. 1073). Hence, ISO specifies the minimal requirements that any organisation must comply with to give confidence that its processes are consistent and systematic actions are taken to guarantee the reproducibility of what has been prescribed in the documentation. The literature also suggests that organisations can reap the benefits from ISO implementation if they see it as an opportunity to organise and improve internal operations and quality in a consistent manner as a part of TQM strategy (Fotopoulos et al., 2010; Lambert & Ouedraogo, 2008).

The literature suggests two main motives that push organisations to obtain the ISO quality certification, namely external related and internal related. External related motives include customer pressures, possibility to access specific markets, and improvements in firms' image and reputation. Internal related motives include the necessity to simplify and standardise a set of processes, productivity improvement, and a better definition of jobs (Karapetrovic et al., 2010). In this regard, Kuo et al. (2009) suggest that as most competitors in the industries that

require ISO registration are already registered, organisations are now looking for internal benefits from the standards.

The literature emphasizes the importance of people involvement in quality processes and systems to maintain the designed quality and make continuous improvements in quality in gaining internal benefits (Dahlgaard et al., 2011; Zink, 2008; Joiner, 2007; Bou & Beltrán, 2005). For instance, Bou and Beltrán (2005, p. 72) state that the people management strategy should be used to develop, through psychological links, committed employees who can be given responsibility to carry out tasks in accordance with the organisational purposes. Therefore, quality management systems should give greater weight to human factors in designing respective work systems (Dahlgaard-Park, 2012; Zelnik et al., 2012; Zink, 2008; Joiner, 2007; Bou & Beltrán, 2005). The literature also suggests that as the implementation of a quality system is a decision taken at the top level of the organisation, the support of the organisation for the process is vital for success (Joiner, 2007).

Organisation citizenship behaviour and quality performance. The quality management literature suggests that successful quality system implementations require employees' extra-role behaviour in terms of OCB (Bell & Menguc, 2002; George and Bettenhausen, 1990; Jung & Hong, 2008). For instance, existing employees' citizenship behaviour may lead to orient new employees to the quality environment at a faster pace (Bell & Menguc, 2002). Further, OCB enhances co-worker productivity and the efficient operation of groups (Jung & Hong, 2008). Furthermore, George and Bettenhausen (1990) state that customer orientation, which is one of the key elements in quality management systems, can be sustained by product provider's extra role behaviours.

However, we have not come across previous research that investigated the outcomes of OCB in organisations that have implemented quality management systems. Based on the literature reviewed above, it is proposed for the study that OCB (in terms of both OCB-I and OCB-O) is positively related to quality performance. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3a: OCB-I is positively related to quality performance

H3b: OCB-O is positively related to quality performance

The main intention of the study is to investigate the mediating effect of OCB (in terms of OCB-I and OCB-O) in the relationship between POS and quality performance and employee engagement and quality performance. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated these links in the quality management literature. However, based on the above reviewed literature on “POS and OCB”, “employee engagement and OCB”, and “OCB and quality performance” we propose following hypotheses (two for OCB-I and two for OCB-O) to test the mediation relationship.

H4a: OCB-I mediates the relationship between POS and quality performance

H4b: OCB-O mediates the relationship between POS and quality performance

H5a: OCB-I mediates the relationship between employee engagement and quality performance

H5b: OCB-O mediates the relationship between employee engagement and quality performance

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed relationships (simplified).

Figure 1. Proposed research model (simplified)

Methodology

Sample

The target population for the study is a cross-section of shop-floor employees employed full-time in ISO 9001:2000 certified manufacturing firms in which the quality management system is in operation for at least 1 year in Sri Lanka. 12 firms willingly participated in the survey. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected shop-floor employees to be participated in this study. In doing so, attempts were made to select a cross-section of shop-floor employees from each firm. Further, participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. Four hundred survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 10% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. 255 usable responses resulted in 64% response rate. The responded firms belong to cable, gasket and solid tyre, radial tyre, polythene bags, electric accessories, school accessories, and floor tile manufacturing industries. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample characteristics

Age (in years):	
Mean	31
S.D.	8
Gender:	
Male	85%
Female	14%
Marital status:	
Single	58%
Married	41%
Highest level of education:	
Up to 10 years	63%
Up to 13 years	37%
Experience in present workplace (in years):	
Mean	8
S.D.	6
Number of employees in the present workplace:	
200 to 400	33%
More than 400	67%
Years of business existence:	
Mean	35
S.D.	12
The age of ISO certification	
5 to 10 years	60%
More than 10 years	40%

Measures

Independent, dependent, and mediator variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For all measurement scales, Cronbach's alpha (α) was examined and principal components factor analysis (varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (refer to Hair et al., 2006).

Perceived organisation support was measured using the eight-item scale of Eisenberger et al. (1997) (for the measurement scale, refer to Eisenberger et al., 1997). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where $\alpha = 0.873$, explained variation = 67.23%, and AVE = .61. Organisation citizenship behaviour was measured using the 14-item scale of Williams and Anderson (1991) (for the measurement scale, refer to Williams & Anderson, 1991). The 14-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.768. As expected factor analysis yielded two factors representing the dimensions of OCB-I ($\alpha = 0.758$, explained variation = 39.53%, and AVE = .54) and OCB-O ($\alpha = 0.744$, explained variation = 24.80%, and AVE = .55). The two factors together explained 64% (64.33) of the variance.

Quality performance was measured by the 13-item scale developed for this study based on the literature reviewed earlier. Factor analysis yielded three factors as shown in Table 2. Factor 1 was labelled as "Manufacturing performance" ($\alpha = 0.837$ and AVE = .50), Factor 2 as "Conformance" ($\alpha = 0.783$ and AVE = .57), and Factor 3 as "First time pass rate" ($\alpha = 0.713$ and AVE = .59).

Table 2. Factor analysis – quality performance

	F1 Manufacturing performance	F2 Conformance	F3 First time pass rate
In our view, quality should be designed into a product, rather than defects inspected out after the fact	.769		
We take initiatives to reduce production time	.765		
We are aggressively working to lower setup times in our plant	.762		
We ensure that product will be manufactured to promise date	.656		
Our workers practice setups to reduce the time required	.642		
Work output by peers is consistently delivered timely	.590		
We believe that prevention is preferable to inspection for quality improvement	.585		
We ensure the degree of conformity of our products with specifications		.858	
We ensure meeting pre-established physical and performance characteristics		.734	
We adheres to work instructions/guidelines when manufacturing products		.674	
We are capable of manufacturing products right the first time			.791
No change or rework needed after final product is manufactured			.793
Work output by peers is consistently delivered accurately			.726
Explained variation	41.61%	10.64%	8.27%
Eigenvalue	5.41	1.38	1.08

In addition, data relating to five individual demographic characteristics and three firm characteristics were collected. The individual demographic characteristics were gender, marital status, the years of experience in the present workplace, age in years, and the highest level of education. The firm characteristics were the number of employees, the years of business existence, and the age of ISO certification (refer to Table 3).

Methods of data collection and analysis

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. The prior studies conducted in Sri Lanka reported that the measurement scales used for the present study are valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context (Amarakoon, 2008; Wickramasinghe, 2008).

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights problems of response bias and multicollinearity (Chang et al, 2010; Conway and Lance, 2010; Reio, 2010; Hair et al., 2006; Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector 1994). Hence, recommended procedural and statistical measures were taken to check whether multicollinearity and response bias were issues in our data (refer to Chang et al, 2010; Conway and Lance, 2010; Podsakoff et al., 2003; Reio, 2010; Spector 1994). First, as detailed earlier, we established construct validity by using widely cited and thoroughly researched measures and by providing appropriate a) reliability, b) factor structure with loadings above .7, c) convergent validity with AVE values above .5, and d) discriminant validity (refer to Table 3). Second, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. Third, Harman's single-factor test was conducted to check whether variance in the data can largely be attributed to a single factor; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance. Finally, variance inflation factors (VIF) were calculated and those were between 1.20 to 2.78. Overall, the results of these tests revealed that multicollinearity and response bias were not issues in our data.

With regard to methods of data analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16.

Results

Table 3 shows descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations between variables. The square root of AVE for each construct is also shown in Table 3. As the square root of AVE for a given construct is greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs, the discriminant validity seems adequate.

Table 3. Correlations

	Me an	S. D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	$\frac{1}{5}$
1 Gender†	.85	.35	-														
2 Age‡	30.78	7.84	.300**	-													
3 Marital status†	.58	.49	.221**	.551**	-												
4 Experience‡	7.73	6.63	.174**	.813**	.411**	-											
5 Education†	.36	.48	.147*	.280**	.120	.254**	-										
6 Employees‡	.67	.46	.286**	.060	.037	.028	.062	-									
7 ISO duration‡	.39	.49	.334**	.271**	.221**	.296**	.087	.563**	-								
8 Business existence‡	35.06	11.95	.334**	.227**	.182**	.237**	.145*	.623**	.641**	-							
9 POS	3.57	.68	.058	.073	.156*	.030	.113	.103	.221**	.130*	.78						
10 Employee engagement	3.60	.63	.162**	.029	.100	.056	.036	.044	.138*	.086	.569**	.71					
11 OCB-I	4.46	.44	.067	.075	.063	.110	.052	.069	.028	.009	.300**	.356**	.73				
12 OCB-O	4.23	.43	.096	.017	.016	.068	.043	.028	.158*	.118	.148*	.133*	.418**	.74			
13 Manufacturing performance	4.06	.53	.048	.030	.045	.057	.015	.104	.184**	.102	.364**	.384**	.494**	.173*	.70		

14	Conformance	4.23	.56	.004	.004	.042	.031	.004	.062	.164**	.028	.444**	.350**	.353**	.163*	.525**	.75
15	First time pass rate	3.91	.80	.195**	.057	.104	.064	.071	.015	.230**	.127*	.288**	.347**	.312**	.197*	.508**	.457

Note: † binary coded, ‡ continuous scale

** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Diagonal entries shown in bold italics from POS to First time pass rate: square root of AVE.

Fit measures of Chi-square, GFI, CFI, and RMSEA were used to evaluate the structural model.

The structural model achieved a good level of fit having a Chi-square = 92.74, CMIN/df = 6.547,

CFI = 0.893 and RMSEA = 0.052. The summary of SEM results is provided in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the results - structural model coefficients

Path	Result	Standardized regression estimate - Direct effect	Standardized regression estimate - Indirect effect
POS → OCB-I	H1a Supported	.144*	-
Employee engagement → OCB-I	H2a Supported	.275***	-
OCB-I → Manufacturing performance		.391***	-
OCB-I → Conformance	H3a supported	.242***	-
OCB-I → First time pass rate		.216***	-
POS → Manufacturing performance	Partial mediation	.158*	.056
POS → Conformance	Partial mediation	.372***	.035
POS → First time pass rate	Full mediation	.001	.131
Employee engagement → Manufacturing performance	Partial mediation	.155*	.108
Employee engagement → Conformance	Full mediation	.002	.166
Employee engagement → First time pass rate	Partial mediation	.270***	.059

Significant paths are shown. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

As can be seen from Table 4, POS has positive and significant relationship with OCB-I, supporting H1a. However, the relationship between POS and OCB-O is non-significant. This does not support H1b.

Employee engagement has positive and significant relationship with OCB-I, supporting H2a. However, the relationship between employee engagement and OCB-O is non-significant. This does not support H2b.

OCB-I has positive and significant relationship with the three components of quality performance (i.e., manufacturing performance, conformance, and first time pass rate), supporting H3a. However, the relationship between OCB-O and the three components of quality performance is non-significant. This does not support H3b.

The main objective of the study was to investigate the mediating effect of OCB in the relationship between POS and quality performance and employee engagement and quality performance. As the relationship between OCB-O and the three components of quality performance is non-significant, H4b and H5b are not supported by the data.

Hypothesis 4a predicted that OCB-I will mediate the relationship between POS and quality performance. As can be seen from Table 4, in addition to the direct relationship between POS and manufacturing performance, there is an indirect relationship between POS and manufacturing performance through OCB-I, suggesting partial mediation. Similarly, in addition to the direct relationship between POS and conformance, there is an indirect relationship between POS and conformance through OCB-I, suggesting partial mediation. As the direct relationship between POS and first time pass rate is not significant, OCB-I fully mediates the relationship between POS and first time pass rate. Therefore, H4a is supported by the data.

Hypothesis 5a predicted that OCB-I will mediate the relationship between employee engagement and quality performance. As can be seen from Table 4, in addition to the direct relationship between employee engagement and manufacturing performance, there is an indirect relationship between employee engagement and manufacturing performance through OCB-I, suggesting partial mediation. Similarly, in addition to the direct relationship between employee engagement and first time pass rate, there is an indirect relationship between employee engagement and first time pass rate through OCB-I, suggesting partial mediation. As the direct relationship between employee engagement and conformance is not significant, OCB-I fully mediates the relationship between employee engagement and conformance. Therefore, H5a is supported by the data.

Squared multiple correlation of .141 suggested that POS and employee engagement accounted for 14% of the variation of OCB-I. Squared multiple correlation of .310 suggested that OCB-I, POS, and employee engagement accounted for 31% of the variation of manufacturing performance. Squared multiple correlation of .251 suggested that OCB-I, POS, and employee engagement accounted for 25% of the variation of conformance. Squared multiple correlation of .161 suggested that OCB-I, POS, and employee engagement accounted for 16% of the variation of first time pass rate.

Conclusions and implications

While it is recognised the importance of people for successful quality management, the literature provides little empirical evidence on the effects of human dimension on quality performance as manifested in the attitudes and expectations of employees.

The study empirically investigated the two component model of OCB, which includes OCB-I and OCB-O, in the context of quality management. It was found that both POS and employee engagement significantly and positively predict OCB-I. This suggests, on the one hand, that employees' positive perceptions towards organisation support influence them to engage more in extra-role behaviour that is not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system but immediately benefit other individuals at work. On the other hand, employees' engagement in physically, cognitively, and emotionally during their role performances influence them to perform extra-role behaviour that immediately benefit other individuals at work.

The study investigated the mediating effect of OCB-I in the relationship between POS and quality performance as well as employee engagement and quality performance. It was found that OCB-I mediates both of the relationships as predicted. This implies that employees' extra-role behaviour in turn influences to enhance the quality performance of the organisations.

The literature suggests that although employees' OCB-O behaviour that goes above and beyond the job does not necessarily directly contribute to the genotypic function of an organisation, those are vital to the organisational effectiveness (Williams & Anderson, 1991). However, the findings suggest that neither POS nor employee engagement operate as an antecedent to OCB-O. This finding is of special concern. This situation questions with respect to what causes employees to take actions that go above and beyond their formal job requirements to help other individuals in the organisation (OCB-I) but not to engage in behaviour that benefit the organisation in general (OCB-O). In this regard, Lambert (2000) also found that POS had a non-significant relationship with OCB. Specifically, Lambert (2000) found that the relationship between POS and both attending a quality meeting and helping others on the job were non-

significant. Lambert (2000) argues that this unanticipated relationship between POS and the measures of citizenship behaviour may imply that POS does not necessarily produce the obligation to reciprocate, as scholars have postulated. However, Lambert (2000) did not differentiate the concepts of OCB-I and OCB-O in that study. Further, although Bergeron (2007) did not differentiate the concepts of OCB-I and OCB-O, Bergeron (2007) argued that OCB, in general, may come at the expense of in-role performance. According to Bergeron (2007) as individuals have limited time, any time spent on OCB comes at the expense of task performance. However, in the work environment organisations favour in-role performance more than OCB. This situation is explicit in previous studies, which provided evidence that in-role performance is weighted more heavily than OCB in determining performance evaluations (Allen & Rush, 1998), rewards (Allen & Rush, 1998), and career advancement (Van Scotter et al. 2000). This suggests that spending time on OCB is good for the organisation but costly for the individual (Bergeron, 2007). In this context, it is possible to argue in the context of the current study that even though it is costly for the individual to spend time in OCB-I activities (e.g. helps others who have been absent, helping colleagues who have heavier work loads, takes a personal interest in other employees), they do so considering their fellow employees. Yet, they do not find sufficient time to engage in OCB-O activities that are not required but which improve organisational (or sub system) image and performance.

The findings have implications for both theory and practice. First, there is surprisingly little empirical research that investigated the two component model of OCB and its antecedents and consequences in the quality management literature. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated the aspects studied in this research to make straight forward

comparisons. Therefore, the findings of our study make a contribution to the literature. However, a considerable future research is necessary to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Yet, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Second, the findings suggest that an environment of support within the organisation promotes extra-role behaviour in employees which enhances quality performance. This finding implies the need of creating an environment which gives employees a feeling that the organisation values their contributions and cares about their welfare.

Third, the findings of the study imply that organisations should take steps to fully engage employees physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances. This will influence employees to perform more extra-role behaviours which will in turn enhance quality performance. However, if employees do not feel there is sufficient acknowledgement and support from the organisation and if they are not engaged physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances, then extra-role behaviours may not emerge and as a consequence firms may not reap the optimal benefits.

Fourth, managers involved in the quality management should be able to cultivate the feelings of acknowledgement and support from the organisation for employees' contributions and fully engage them in role performance. Sometimes, managers may need special training to deepen their knowledge on the concepts of POS, employee engagement, and OCB in the context of quality management.

Finally, the finding that POS and employee engagement do not predict OCB-O implies that organisations need to find a win-win situation in which individuals can engage in activities

that leads to OCB-O and still have positive outcomes in terms of performance evaluations, rewards, and career advancement. This implies the need of ensuring that organisational performance evaluations, rewards, and career advancement systems take into account employees' extra-role behaviours. Therefore, organisations should design human resource management systems to ensure that employees' extra-role behaviours are adequately recognized by the organisation.

Limitations and future research

First, the research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. We have not differentiated firms in terms of the size in this study. Future research could incorporate such variables for comparison. Further, future research could include the duration of ISO certification as a variable for comparison. Furthermore, future research studies in different samples that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data may provide more insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

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